

Examining the Impact of Ethical Leadership in Unions on Employee Pro-Organizational Behavior: A Study on the Relationship with Unethical Conduct"

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Abstract: Unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB) is a topic of significant interest in leadership research. This paper introduces trade union moral leadership as a novel antecedent variable of employee UPB and examines its moderating effect on the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB, based on the concept of "dual organizational moral situation-employee behavior." The study surveyed 211 enterprise trade union members and found that: one There is an inverted U-shaped relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB, with trade union moral leadership having an additional inhibitory effect; two Trade union moral leadership has a negative buffering effect on the curve relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB. As the level of trade union moral leadership increases, the negative impact of corporate moral leadership on UPB weakens; three Trade union moral leadership has a positive moderating effect on the curve relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB. As the level of trade union moral leadership increases, the curve between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB reverses to a diminishing marginal trend. These findings not only contribute to research on factors that can inhibit UPB but also provide practical guidance for enterprises to improve moral leadership management and avoid moral hazard.

Keywords: unethical pro-organizational behavior, union moral leadership, social cognitive.

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1: Introduction

Organizational managers and researchers have become increasingly concerned about the lack of morality exhibited by employees who deliberately conceal product defects or engage in false advertising to protect their companies' interests. This behavior is referred to as unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB), define it as behavior intended to benefit the

organization or its members but that violates core values, morals, laws, or reasonable behavioral standards of society. UPB is dangerous because it is often overlooked by organizations in the guise of being "pro-organization," and its essential immorality poses significant hidden risks to the sustainable and healthy development of businesses. Leadership plays a crucial role in shaping the organizational environment, and can strengthen corporate ethics and guidelines by implementing appropriate reward and punishment measures. This approach can influence employees' moral cognition and decision-making processes [1]. There is a strong correlation between corporate ethical leadership and unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB) among employees. Previous studies have demonstrated that ethical leaders who treat their employees fairly, respectfully, and with trust tend to foster positive work attitudes and behaviors. However, this also leads to employees being driven by high levels of corporate identity and return motivation, resulting in UPB. The primary reason for this is that ethical leaders fail to continuously convey clear moral messages to their employees, raising doubts about their effectiveness in regulating employees' moral behavior. Therefore, finding a new way to effectively control and manage employee UPB is becoming increasingly urgent [2]. The "Trade Union Law of the People's Republic of China" and the "Articles of Association of Chinese Trade Unions" mandate that trade unions must organize and educate employees to exercise their democratic rights in compliance with the provisions of the Constitution and laws. The objective is to continuously enhance employees' ideological and moral, technical, professional, and scientific and cultural capabilities. The functional role of leadership in employee moral education is critical. Several studies have indicated that reform measures such as open recruitment of trade union chairpersons, professionalization of trade union chairpersons, and post specialization have significantly boosted the influence of trade unions in corporate management practices. As a result, trade union leaders have become important participants in workplace activities [3]. According to research the leadership of the trade union chairperson is directly related to the actual status and functional performance of the trade union in the enterprise. The trade union leader serves as a "balancing function mechanism" between enterprise development and employee rights and interests [4]. However, there is still a lack of compelling research findings. In the Chinese context, trade union leaders assume multiple roles in social governance, enterprise management, and employee services, and are not motivated by a single objective [5]. In light of this, the ethical leadership of trade unions emphasizes not only the integration and balance of moral values and corporate management practices but also the improvement of communication and interaction between companies and employees through labor law supervision, negotiation, education, and training. This can guide employees to make decisions and take actions that align with ethical standards and benefit all parties involved. It is evident that Chinese enterprise employees are embedded in the dual leadership situations of enterprise and trade union leaders. According to the social cognitive theory of moral thought and action [6], UPB may still occur even under the leadership of enterprise moral leadership due to the ambiguity of moral information conveyed. However, the moral leadership of trade unions serves as an information link between the enterprise and employees, acting as a "bridge" that corrects employees' moral cognition and judgment. This is a source of motivation for employees to regulate their own behavior when confronted with moral dilemmas. Therefore, introducing trade union moral leadership to explore the mechanism and boundary conditions of UPB is of significant practical importance [7]. In summary, this paper's research value lies in several aspects. Firstly, it proposes that trade union moral leadership can serve as an important way for companies to prevent employee UPB, which fills the gap in existing research on the inhibitory factors of UPB and uncovers the fundamental reasons for its repeated occurrence in the workplace. Secondly, this study explores the buffering and corrective effect of trade union moral leadership on the curvilinear relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB, responding to the call for responsible research. Thirdly, based on the "dual organizational moral situation-employee behavior" logic, it proposes a dual-subject perspective of ethical leadership in enterprises and trade unions and develops a theoretical framework for its impact on employee UPB, contributing new knowledge to the integration of human resource management research and labor relations research. Finally, this paper provides guidance for the construction of flexible, dynamic, and efficient ethical management models in practice by clarifying the collaborative and interactive relationship between corporate moral leadership and trade union moral leadership.

2. Literature review and hypothesis

2.1. Corporate moral leadership and unethical pro-organizational

Corporate moral leadership entails that business executives uphold ethical principles in their personal conduct and interpersonal interactions, and encourage ethical behavior among employees through effective communication, reinforcement, and decision-making. It necessitates leaders to possess integrity, authenticity, and moral qualities such as altruism and a sense of accountability, thereby setting ethical examples and establishing moral benchmarks in the workplace. Previous research has primarily emphasized the benefits of corporate moral leadership, contending that prioritizing ethical norms and guidelines can discourage employees from engaging in unethical conduct [8]. recent research indicates that employees working under ethical corporate leadership may perceive a discrepancy between moral standards and corporate interests, leading to confusion in their moral decision-making and increasing the likelihood of engaging in unethical behavior. Unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB) is a unique form of unethical conduct that reflects the imbalance and confusion in employees' moral cognitive mechanisms. As a means for companies to establish and convey their moral norms and guidelines, the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB has become an area of interest for scholars. Previous studies suggest that corporate moral leadership serves as a source of moral information and can regulate employee moral decision-making by serving as role models and providing moral supervision. However, it can also lead to employees highly identifying with the company, creating a dilemma between protecting the organization's interests and adhering to ethical standards. It is apparent that while corporate moral leadership plays a critical role in transmitting and demonstrating moral information, its impact on employee UPB has both positive and negative effects [9]. Employee UPB is primarily influenced by the characteristics of the organizational moral context as it stems from an individual's cognitive processing and behavioral decision-making on moral information in the workplace. According to Bandura's social cognitive theory of moral concepts and actions, individuals perceive, observe, and assess moral information and cues in organizational situations as "human agencies" to make moral decisions. However, in the organizational context, corporate moral leadership cannot consistently convey moral requirements. This is because employees' awareness and understanding of corporate moral leadership's status undergo periodic changes. The moral cognition process of employees under corporate moral leadership typically goes through three stages: weak motivation, information ambiguity, and moral reinforcement. Weak motivation occurs when employees perceive a negative corporate image under low-level corporate moral leadership and are reluctant to take additional moral hazards for corporate interests. Information ambiguity arises when corporate moral leaders have a "medium-level trap," which can mislead employees to adopt unethical behaviors that benefit the enterprise. Moral reinforcement occurs under high-level corporate moral leadership, where moral standards are strengthened by instilling moral values and beliefs in employees, formulating moral reward and punishment policies, and enhancing moral sensitivity [10]. This reduces the likelihood of employees engaging in UPB. Employee UPB exhibits an inverted U-shaped pattern with increasing levels of corporate moral leadership, where corporate moral leadership can only inhibit UPB when it reaches a certain threshold (inflection point). Based on this analysis, we propose the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis One is that the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB follows an inverted U-shaped pattern.

2.2. Function of labor union leadership

In China, the nature and characteristics of trade unions are significantly different from those of foreign trade unions. As a result, Chinese trade union leaders have unique roles in the workplace. While foreign studies suggest that trade unions act as both "monopolies" that demand wage increases and "collective spokespersons" for employee concerns, this conclusion does not apply to Chinese trade unions. Chinese trade union leaders mainly act as "party and government spokespersons" and are more moderate in dealing with enterprises and employees as "collective spokespersons." Based on their functional positioning, trade union leaders play a "flexible" and "friendly" role in coordinating the interests of employees and enterprises [11]. National labor laws, regulations, and policies emphasize the leading role of trade union leaders in educating employees and organizing their training. With the emergence of new forms and models of labor

relations, companies have also recognized the value of trade unions in promoting labor-management communication and understanding employee needs [12].

Although previous research has shown the role of trade union leaders in improving employee welfare and positive work behaviors, such as trade union participation and Union Citizenship Behavior, it has focused on traditional rights protection activities. As a result, trade union leaders' important role in balancing the interests of the enterprise and employees has been overlooked. However, Chinese enterprise trade unions have shed the labels of "shell trade unions" and "corporate appendages" and have gradually expanded their responsibilities. The All-China Federation of Trade Unions has promulgated many laws and regulations on trade union cadres' protection, the collection of trade union funds, and the qualifications of trade union chairmen. Against this background, labor union reform experiences and models, such as the socialization of enterprise labor union leaders, full-time professionalization, and direct election of labor unions, continue to emerge [13].

This article focuses on the professionalization of trade union leaders in China and explores the differential impact and mechanism of these two leadership factors on employee UPB from the perspective of dual subjects of enterprise leaders and trade union leaders [14]. The positive role of trade union leaders in building healthy workplace relationships and improving employee work behavior needs to be re-examined in the context of China's trade union system and mechanism innovation.

2.3 Effect of trade union moral leadership on unethical pro-organizational

China's enterprise trade union is a unique organization that operates within the enterprise and acts as a "partner" to guide employees' moral behavior and promote social responsibility. The morality of trade union leaders is essential in their role as a "spokesperson" and organizer of trade union activities. Due to their position within a network of multiple forces such as the government, enterprises, and employees, Chinese trade unions prioritize the coordination and balance of various subject interests. The root cause of unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB) is the difficulty employees face in balancing the interest requirements from the enterprise and the moral expectations from external stakeholders. Trade union moral leadership can help supervise the enterprise's moral management and ensure it adheres to social moral norms, which is an important pathway to preventing UPB [15].

According to the social cognitive theory of moral concepts and actions, individuals are influenced by multiple moral standards and requirements in the organizational environment, which are complementary and synergistic. When employees are under the organizational situation of both corporate moral leadership and trade union moral leadership, they are directly affected by corporate moral leadership while also under the signal of trade union moral leadership, adjusting their actions based on the trade union leaders' moral cognition and expectations. Trade union ethical leadership can play an "incremental" role in the transmission and communication of corporate moral information, which is difficult for companies to resolve due to the ethical conflict between economic interests and social responsibilities. Trade union moral leadership also emphasizes the integration and balance of moral values and corporate management practices, improving employees' moral awareness and behavior from an organizational level. As the link and bridge between enterprises and employees, trade union moral leadership plays a vital role in connecting internal and external interest groups, gradually forming a consensus on the organization's ethical policies, procedures, and practices. Employees are influenced by positive values conveyed by trade union ethical leadership, internalizing them and externalizing them in their actions, making ethical decisions that meet various needs. The ethical leadership of trade unions can assist managers in injecting moral concepts and value orientations into all aspects of corporate management practice, playing a greater role in avoiding employees' moral dilemmas than corporate moral leadership. Based on this, it can be hypothesized that trade union moral leadership can inhibit the occurrence of UPB [16].

The second hypothesis posits that in addition to corporate moral leadership, the moral leadership of trade unions also plays a significant role in restraining employee unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB).

2.4. Impact of trade union moral leadership on CML and UPB

The theory of social cognition regarding moral concepts and actions highlights the dynamic nature of employees' moral awareness and cognition, which is context-dependent and influenced by various organizational situations [17]. As per

this theory, when faced with conflicting organizational needs, employees who have adequate resources and strategies will have a higher level of consistency between their moral judgments and behavioral choices. The moral leadership of trade unions, as a concentrated expression of their moral values, has a significant impact on the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employees' moral judgment and cognition. This impact depends on the level of corporate moral leadership, and a curvilinear relationship exists between corporate moral leadership and employee unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB) [18].

When corporate moral leadership is low, trade union moral leadership acts as a supplement by helping organizations deliver clear moral information and supervising employee work behavior. When corporate moral leadership is at a medium level, trade union moral leadership helps to provide clearer ethical evaluation criteria, reduce ambiguity and divergence, and provide a greater sense of moral sensitivity, leading to more positive protection of organizational interests by employees. However, when corporate moral leadership is high, trade union moral leadership has a substitution effect in the transmission of moral information. At this point, the UPB level of employees decreases under the moral supervision and demonstration of corporate moral leadership [19].

Trade union moral leadership, with its core goals of labor education, professional ethics publicity, and participation in corporate moral management, stimulates the moral potential of employees, which has a corrective effect on the curve relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB. By protecting employees' right to speak, building an internal communication system, and promoting employee participation, trade unions can effectively balance the interest connection mechanism between the enterprise and employees, reducing perceived moral cognitive biases [20]. Hypothesis 3a, the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB is moderated by trade union moral leadership, with a negative effect. This means that as the level of trade union moral leadership increases, the impact of corporate moral leadership on employee UPB decreases, while a decline in trade union moral leadership leads to an increase in the effect of corporate moral leadership on employee UPB.

Hypothesis 3b predicts that a higher level of trade union moral leadership will shift the curve between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB to the left as a whole, while a lower level of trade union moral leadership will move the curve to the right as a whole. In other words, the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB will be stronger or weaker depending on the level of trade union moral leadership, with a greater impact observed when trade unions have lower levels of moral leadership.

3. Research methods

3.1 Data collection

To ensure the suitability of the research questions and a comprehensive understanding of corporate moral leadership and trade union moral leadership, this paper follows the principle of "theoretical sampling" to select sample companies and gather research data. The selection criteria for sample companies include: having a leading position in the industry, possessing a sound human resource management system, and covering a range of enterprise types such as state-owned, private, foreign-funded, and collectively owned enterprises to enhance the generalization of the conclusions.

Due to the dual identities of labor union leaders, this paper focuses on grassroots employees who serve as trade union leaders or chairmen to improve the robustness of the research conclusions. The paper selects Eleven representative enterprises with good trade union construction in different regions and industries through enterprise interviews and pre-research.

To reduce homogeneous variance, the paper collects data from business leaders, trade union leaders, and ordinary employees through email and on-site recycling. The survey questionnaires cover the position of the trade union chairperson in the corporate organizational structure, the selection method of the corporate trade union chairperson, and the evaluation of leaders and union-perceived behaviors (UPB). The researchers collected 211 survey questionnaires, of which 180 were valid, with an 85.3% efficiency rate. The study includes male and female employees, with the majority being aged 18 to 32 and having a college degree or above.

To ensure the accuracy of the data, the researchers used various control methods, such as inviting experts, MBA students, and experienced corporate employees to evaluate the questionnaire, and communicating with senior management and human resources departments to gain support and cooperation from the survey respondents.

3.2 Experiment analysis tools

To ensure the validity of the measurement scale, this paper utilizes the variable measurement scale that is widely used and recognized by scholars in existing literature. The Likert five-point scoring system is used for all scales, with scores ranging from "one" to "five" to indicate the degree of compliance with the described situation, from low to high. Additionally, the "translation-back translation" procedure is employed to ensure the understanding and validity of the measurement scale to the greatest extent.

1: Unethical pre-organizational behavior

The self-assessment scale for UPB used in this article is based on and consists of six items [20]. An example item from the scale is "I would exaggerate the company's products or services to clients or others if it would help our company." The reliability of the scale is evaluated using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, and in this study, the scale demonstrates high internal consistency with a coefficient of 0.91.

2: Trade union moral leadership

Corporate moral leadership and labor union moral leadership are both considered leadership styles. To measure trade union moral leadership, this study adapted the corporate moral leadership scale developed. by rephrasing the items, for instance, "My trade union leader will punish employees who violate the Code of Ethics." The internal consistency of the scale was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, and the scale demonstrates high reliability with a coefficient of 0.95 in this study.

3: Enterprise moral leadership

The Moral Leadership Scale developed, is utilized in this study, which comprises of seven items [21]. Examples of the items include "My business leader takes action against employees who breach the ethical code." The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the scale is 0.961 in this paper.

4: Control variables

This paper considers demographic variables such as gender, age, education, party membership, enterprise nature, and enterprise scale as control variables. Moreover, prior research indicates that the identity difference between direct and indirect elections of trade union leaders and employees' perceived independence of trade unions impact individual attitudes towards trade unions, as well as the role and status of trade unions in organizations. Accordingly, this study treats these factors as control variables.

4. Research results

4.1 Evaluation of measurement validity

To ensure the validity of the measurement and distinguish between highly correlated concepts, this study conducts a confirmatory factor analysis and compares a series of models. Confirmatory factor analysis is employed to test the discriminant validity among the variables. Table 1 presents the fitting indices of each model. The results indicate that the 3-factor model fits the data best ($\chi^2=411.109$, $df=132$, $CFI=0.957$, $TLI=0.952$, $RMSEA=0.082$, $SRMR=0.046$), which is consistent with the standards recognized by the academic community and outperforms other alternative models. Conversely, the single factor model shows the worst fit ($\chi^2=2016.333$, $df=135$, $CFI=0.631$, $TLI=0.639$, $RMSEA=0.245$, $SRMR=0.201$), demonstrating that the research variables have strong discriminant validity. please provide the table

Table1: Evaluation of Measurement Validity

Model	χ^2	df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA	SRMR
Single factor model	2016.333	135	0.631	0.639	0.245	0.201
Two-factor model	1232.324	137	0.772	0.812	0.231	0.071
Three-factor model	411.109	132	0.957	0.952	0.082	0.046

Note: χ^2 is the chi-square statistic, df is the degrees of freedom, CFI is the comparative fit index, TLI is the Tucker-Lewis index, RMSEA is the root mean square error of approximation, and SRMR is the standardized root mean square residual. The three-factor model fits the data best and shows strong discriminant validity.

4.2 Common method bias

To address potential method bias in the research, the study utilized the potential error variable control method, which involves controlling for the effects of a single unmeasured latent method factor. The measurement model structure was used to establish a structural model predicting employee UPB by corporate moral leadership and trade union moral leadership. To test for common method bias, a latent variable representing common method bias was added to the model, and all observed indicators of the latent variables in the model were loaded onto this variable. Additionally, a method latent factor was added to the original confirmatory factor analysis model, causing all measurement items to load on the method latent factor in addition to their corresponding construct factor. Results showed that the model fit was not significantly improved after adding the common method factor, as evidenced by $\Delta\chi^2/df=0.05$, $\Delta RMSEA=0.002$, and other fitting indices remaining unchanged. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was no substantial difference in measurement due to common method bias.

4.3 Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients among the variables measured in this study. The correlation coefficient between UPB and corporate moral leadership is -0.216 ($p<0.001$), while the correlation coefficient between UPB and trade union moral leadership is -0.217 ($p<0.001$), providing initial support for the study's hypotheses. None of the correlation coefficients among the variables exceeded the critical value of 0.8, suggesting no significant issue of multi-collinearity in the sample data. Furthermore, the variance inflation factor (VIF) values for all variables were less than 10. To enhance the robustness of the research conclusions and minimize potential correlations among variables, mean centering was applied to all variables.

Table2 Descriptive statistics analysis

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	1	2	3
1. UPB	2.761	0.891			
2. Corporate moral leadership	2.764	0.844	-0.216***		
3. Trade union moral leadership	2.821	0.801	-0.217***	0.812***	

Note: *** $p<0.001$. All variables were mean-centered. VIF values were all less than 10.

4.4 Hypothesis testing

The present study employed the hierarchical regression method to examine the research hypothesis, and the results are presented. Model 2 shows that corporate moral leadership has a curvilinear relationship with employee UPB ($\beta=-0.311$, $p<0.001$), providing support for H1. Model 3, while controlling for the influence of corporate moral leadership and its square term, confirms that trade union moral leadership has a significant negative impact on employee UPB ($\beta=-0.216$, $p<0.01$). This suggests that trade union moral leadership has a unique influence on employee UPB beyond the influence of corporate leadership, supporting H2. The study found that trade union moral leadership increased the explanation rate of employee UPB by 2.1% beyond the effect of corporate moral leadership. Moreover, when the moral leadership of the trade union is added, the effect value of the ethical leadership of the enterprise and its square term on the UPB decreases. This suggests that trade union moral leadership plays an intermediary role in the relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee behavior, which is consistent with the role of Chinese trade unions as a bridge in labor relations coordination and communication. The results of Model 4 demonstrate a significant interaction effect between the square term of corporate moral leadership and trade union moral leadership ($\beta=0.317$, $p<0.01$), indicating that trade union moral leadership has a regulatory effect on the curvilinear relationship between corporate moral leadership and UPB. To further analyze the adjustment mechanism, the sample was divided into two groups (with the trade union moral leadership score higher or lower than the average value of one standard deviation), and regression analysis was conducted on the square of corporate moral leadership based on the two groups. As shown in Figure 2, when the trade union moral leadership is high, the curve between corporate moral leadership and UPB is relatively flat,

while when the trade union moral leadership is low, the curve is steep. This supports H3a. Additionally, under low trade union moral leadership, the quadratic coefficient of the curve is significant ($\beta=-0.278$, $p<0.01$), but the fitting degree of the quadratic model is higher than that of the linear model. Under high trade union moral leadership, the curve relationship between corporate moral leadership and employee UPB presents a downward marginal decreasing trend, and the quadratic coefficient of the curve relationship is not significant. Although this finding is not entirely consistent with H3b, it illustrates the corrective effect of trade union moral leadership on the cognitive bias between corporate moral leadership and employees. In summary, a high level of trade union moral leadership can not only compensate for the shortcomings of business leaders in guiding employees' moral behavior, but it can also "reverse" them, resulting in a healthier and more sustainable organization.

5. Conclusions

In this article, the impact of trade union leadership on employees' work attitudes and behaviors is explored from the perspective of social cognitive theory. The study examines the influence of trade union moral leadership, which is a new antecedent variable, on corporate moral leadership and the formation mechanism of unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB). The research concludes that trade union moral leadership plays an important role in regulating employees' behavior and attitudes towards work. Additionally, the study reveals that trade union moral leadership can "partially replace" the guiding role of corporate moral leadership on employees' moral concepts and behaviors, thus mitigating the inverted U-shaped relationship between corporate moral leadership and UPB. The moderating effect of trade union moral leadership varies in different stages of the relationship between corporate moral leadership and UPB. Furthermore, the research finds that trade union moral leaders can supervise and correct misunderstandings of corporate moral leadership, providing employees with fair, safe and healthy workplace conditions. Overall, the research highlights the complex interactive relationship between different leadership styles and employee behaviors and provides new insights into employee UPB management.

contributes to the research on trade union leadership style and its impact on unethical employee behavior from the perspective of labor relations. While scholars have previously focused on the role of trade unions in protecting employee rights and benefits, this paper sheds light on their potential to actively intervene and guide employees towards ethical behavior. By exploring the concept of trade union moral leadership, the paper demonstrates how it can inhibit unethical behavior by guiding employees to balance corporate and social interests and express their interests in an ethical and legal manner. This not only adds to the existing knowledge on trade union leadership but also enriches the understanding of the factors influencing unethical employee behavior.

Additionally, the paper draws on the social cognition theory of moral concepts and actions to show that trade union moral leadership has a "crowding out effect" on corporate moral leadership's ability to induce ethical behavior. Trade union moral leadership serves as a regulator and coordinator that can correct and restrain corporate decision-making and information communication, thereby weakening the relationship between unethical behavior and corporate moral leadership. This emphasizes the importance of considering the role of trade union moral leadership in improving the influence of corporate moral leadership on employee behavior.

The light on the importance of trade union moral leadership in the context of organizational management practice. By demonstrating the inhibitory effect of trade union moral leadership on unethical pro-organizational behavior (UPB), the paper highlights the need for enterprises to adopt more efficient and sustainable methods to standardize and guide employees' moral behavior. This requires a scientific and systematic approach to intervene in employees' UPB process and provide a new path for realization.

The paper also confirms the limitations of corporate moral leadership, as it can set a moral example for employees but may not be accurately recognized or understood by them. In contrast, trade union moral leaders are better equipped to go deep into the employee group and understand their psychological state and basic demands. They can thus help identify the source of unethical incidents in the enterprise more effectively and seek the balance of interests between the enterprise and employees as a third party.

The strategic and methodological guidance for enterprises and trade unions to jointly build an employee moral supervision mechanism. It suggests that trade unions can play a critical role in monitoring and correcting the process of corporate moral leadership-induced UPB and guiding employees to abide by moral norms through caring, inspiration, and demonstration learning. It also emphasizes the importance of providing employees with a platform for feedback and complaints, regularly conducting employee attitude surveys and moral education activities, and establishing a dynamic tracking and evaluation mechanism for employee moral behavior.

The need for trade unions to improve their status and role in employee moral management and better serve the interests of employees. Trade union leaders can do this by transmitting work information and resources to employees, providing them with psychological protection, and improving their work behavior performance. They should also actively promote the disclosure of corporate affairs, corporate supervision and policy formulation, employee professional ethics construction, employee moral education and training, and actively improve the way of interaction with enterprises.

Overall, the paper underscores the importance of trade union moral leadership in enhancing employee moral behavior and promoting healthy and balanced workplace atmosphere. It suggests that business managers should be good at using the "flexible" means of trade union moral leadership to maintain employees' trust and understanding of organizational goals, and jointly create a healthy and balanced workplace atmosphere.

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